

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE JADIDIST MOVEMENT IN THE IMPROVEMENT OF THE SPIRITUAL LIFE OF TURKESTAN

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The Jadidist movement in Turkestan is not a coincidence, but a product of socio-political conflicts in our lives. From the beginning of the 19th century, among the enlightened Muslim clergy and intellectuals of Bukhara, the idea of reforming the heresies that had entered the system of madrasas and schools and the Islamic religion began to emerge. Supporters of such reforms began to be called Jadidists, that is, supporters of innovation. Jadidism (derived from the Arabic word "jadid" and meaning "new"). Since those times, the movement that opposed this, that is, people who were in the spirit of feudal-medievalism and religious fanaticism, began to be called Kadimists. In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, as a result of the strengthening of tsarist colonialism in Turkestan, the Jadid movement gained strength in many parts of Central Asia. Since this movement was aimed at rebuilding the socio-cultural foundations of the existing society, it encountered strong resistance from supporters of the old system, the old way of life, and the old school[1].

Representatives of this opposing force were called kadim or kadimchis, while those who tried to bring the breath of new life were called jadids or jadidchis. Thus, at the beginning of our century, the Jadids and the Jadid movement emerged. In the rich socio-philosophical, religious-moral, and cultural development of the Turkestan people, the period of the first quarter of the 19th century is distinguished by its extremely rich and revolutionary vitality, the diversity of ideological-theoretical, and ideological forms of movement. This was a peculiar direction of

social development. Turkestan was conquered by Russia in the second half of the 19th century and turned into a colony. The main ideas and goals of Jadidism were to free Turkestan from medievalism, feudal backwardness, and superstitions, to lead the country, people, and nation to a modern path of development while rejecting the "Ancient Method", to build a national state, to see a free and prosperous society with a constitutional, parliamentary, and presidential system of government, to give Turkic languages the status of state languages, to create a national currency, and to create opportunities for Russian progressives and enlighteners to spread their enlightened ideas in Turkestan. Thus, the emergence of the Jadidism movement in Turkestan was gradual, albeit based on the ideology of national liberation. This process began to have its impact on the consciousness of the local people in the country. As a result, they managed to prepare the ground for a national liberation movement in Turkestan to fight for independence, national development, and the interests of the people.

Anti-colonialist ideas of enlightenment began to spread among the indigenous peoples, new educational institutions, new schools, enlightenment, cultural propaganda, and the Jadid movement developed[2].

In such conditions, many enlighteners emerged in Turkestan. The Jadid movement in Turkestan operated in three areas. These are:

- education (opening new schools, renewing the method of education);
- art (fiction, theater);
- press (newspapers and magazines)

The main goal was to make the nation, on the one hand, scientifically and enlightened, and on the other hand, to raise its moral level and, as a result of the combination of these two aspects, to raise an educated person who understood his own identity and his own value. The Jadidists of Turkestan did a lot of work to achieve this goal. Along with the historical circumstances, the enlightenment and enlightenment views that arose in the last quarter of the 19th century had a great

influence on the emergence of the Jadidist movement in Turkestan.

If we pay attention to the socio-political and cultural life of Turkestan in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, we see that the ideology of enlightenment constituted the ideological content of democratic and national-patriotic movements. The main reason for the emergence of the idea of enlightenment in our country was, firstly, the deepening of the Russian colonial policy, which national liberation movements that were taking place, secondly, the suppression of democratic movements coming from the West by the invaders, and thirdly, the persecution of nationalist and self-sacrificing people and even their execution.

Representatives of the Jadid movement based their enlightenment ideology on the democratic ideas relevant for that time: studying science, enjoying scientific and technical achievements, developing scientific and natural sciences, introducing freedom of speech and thought, creating a national statehood based on democratic state building, forming a layer of national ideas, developing modern genres of literature and art, and on the other hand, restoring the Turkic language and national values, which were losing their national image under the influence of colonial policies, further strengthening national spiritual and moral improvements, understanding national identity, strengthening national consciousness, national thinking and religious beliefs. Of course, in implementing these tasks, they also rely on the teachings of traditional Islam, the foundations of Sharia law and hadiths, which also retain their influence. The Jadidists tried to implement their progressive ideas among the people by developing national printing, introducing a modern education system, and sending local youth to advanced Western countries to study.

In the early stages of the Turkestan Enlightenment, moral ideas were mainly reflected in artistic and didactic forms. In this regard, the work of the thinkers of the Uzbek and Tajik peoples, “Navodir ul - waqoe” by Ahmad Donish (1827 - 1897), is noteworthy. In his works, Ahmad Donish compares the state system of the Bukhara Emirate with the Russian state system and emphasizes the need to reform

it. At the same time, thinking with traditional moral concepts, he considers justice as a virtue inherent in both the person of the tsar - the ruler and the state system. If the ruler pursues a just policy, makes justice the criterion for all spheres of the country's life, and opens the way for the flourishing of art, the life of the people will be prosperous, virtues will strengthen, and vices will weaken. He concludes that the ruler must necessarily possess the virtue of wisdom, that reason determines the essence of the state: only the population of a rationally governed country can be enlightened and have high morals.

Jadidism is actually a manifestation of the Enlightenment movement. Therefore, we found it necessary to begin the statement of the issue here by explaining the concepts of enlightenment and enlightenment and their significance. The lexical meaning of enlightenment is to know, to be familiar with, to know. In other words, to know enlightenment is an educational process aimed at increasing the consciousness, knowledge, and culture of people. The meaning of the word enlightenment in most people is enlightenment. Enlightenment as a term means a complex of various knowledge and information about nature, society and the essence of man. Enlightened means knowledgeable, having knowledge in a certain field.

In the present era, when sciences are developing deeply and widely, every person, student, and scientist who aspires to knowledge and science can only master a certain field of science, that is, enlightenment. For example, they master a certain field of chemistry, as well as certain areas of mathematics, physics, biology, medicine, and others. The assimilation of enlightenment into life is carried out through the education system. So, enlightenment is the combined content of knowledge and culture, and education is a tool, a means of disseminating this content. Enlightenment is mainly distributed in schools and educational institutions providing general and secondary specialized education. The concept of enlightenment is broader than the concept of education and includes all types, forms

and areas of spreading and improving knowledge and culture. In society, enlightenment, that is, knowledge, is spread through enlighteners. An enlightener means a person who strives for enlightenment; a person who lights the lamp of science and knowledge; a patron and supporter of enlightenment [3]. The transition of humanity from one society to another, from one historical period to another, begins with enlightenment.

The most mature, conscious, selfless, knowledgeable, far-sighted spiritual people of our time are engaged in enlightenment. Enlightenment leaders usually put forward important ideas for the era, for the present and future of society, country, people, and struggle to implement these ideas.

Enlightenment eliminates spiritual dependence, fear and delusion, and endows man with incomparable divine power and unparalleled potential. That is why freedom fighters believe that the freedom of a country and nation lies in the enlightened awakening of the people and fight for enlightenment. Our people have lived in the pursuit of enlightenment since time immemorial. This country has made a huge contribution to the development of world science.

Mahmudkhodja Behbudiy, Munavvar qari Abdurashidkhan oglu, Abdulkadir Shakuriy, Ashurali Zohiriy, Saidrasul Saidaziziyy, Ishaqkhon Ibrat, and Ahmad Donishyy began their activities at the end of the 19th century and considered enlightenment to be the only way to free the country and the people from national oppression and backwardness. These selfless people fought with all their might against the tyrannical system and ignorance, spiritual slavery, and oppression. These enlightened ancestors of ours traveled the world, got acquainted with the scientific culture of the peoples of the world, and deeply felt that it was possible to lead and break the shackles of a colonial country towards freedom only with the light of knowledge. For this reason, first of all, they showed an example of determination and courage in developing school and educational work in our country, both practically and theoretically [4].

From the very first days of their appearance, the Jadids encountered opposition from both the Tsarist government and local rulers. Consequently, they sought to free the people from these two foci of oppression, from these two swamps of backwardness. Abdulla Badri, in his treatise “Who are the Young Bukhara People?”, wrote about the Jadids: “... their intellectual ideas and aspirations are to free us, the poor and the needy, from the oppression of the emirs, beks and the rich, and to work and struggle for our comfort and peace.”

The services of the leader of the Uzbek Jadid movement, Mahmudkhoj Behbudi, in unifying and broadening the ranks of the Jadids, who initially came to the scene mainly with the aim of fulfilling educational tasks, are incomparable. He traveled to several industrial centers of Russia and the Near East to organize a national printing house and publishing house in the future, to get acquainted with the life of neighboring peoples, including schools and education, to study the experience of progressive forces in these countries, and to trace the international relations of Uzbek Jadids.

Through the efforts of the Tarbiyai Atfol society established in Bukhara, Fitrat went to Turkey with his two brothers to study. In conclusion, we must say that Jadidism played a major role in the national awakening and the rise of national consciousness in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. Its bright representatives, such as Behbudiy, Fitrat, Cholpon, Abdulla Qodiriy, Abdulla Avloniy, Munavvarqori, Fayzullo Khojayev, Sofizoda, Tavallo, Ishaqjon Ibrat, tried to promote the ideas of Jadidism in extremely difficult conditions. They did a great job in raising the nation's morale and preventing its dignity from being undermined. Despite severe material difficulties and ideological and political pressures, the enlightened Jadidists tried to create opportunities for the nation's spiritual upliftment. They took on all the work in this regard because they realized that raising the nation's national consciousness and strengthening the sense of national pride in difficult and responsible periods of history were among the top tasks.

Behbudiy, Fitrat, Munavvarqori and other Jadidists who were passionate about the nation opened schools, taught there themselves, wrote and published textbooks, and showed dedication in this regard. They did not even spare their own money on this path. Such noble deeds as generosity and meritoriousness are extremely necessary for our current independent development. Today, the invaluable works, scientific, poetic and prose heritage of the enlighteners-Jadidists, their socio-philosophical and moral ideas serve to raise the spirituality and enlightenment, national values and consciousness of the Uzbek people, and instill in the hearts of generations feelings of love and loyalty to the Motherland.

Thanks to independence, the names of the enlighteners-Jadidists are being restored, their birthdays are being solemnly celebrated, and their works are being published again and again. The philosophical and moral thoughts expressed in their worldviews are still preserved as cultural and spiritual values of our people.

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